

Bridging Gap: Citizen Engagement in Local Governance in Nepal

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Abstract

Citizen-state engagement is a key component of inclusive and participatory governance, ensuring that local decisions reflect the views and needs of grassroots-level people. In Nepal, both government and non-governmental organizations have made it a priority for citizens to be involved in local planning and discussions, as well as in the formulation of necessary legal documents and projects. However, the study notes that people have not engaged actively, which makes them worry about how well these activities are working. The objective of this study is to explore the opportunities and challenges of citizens' participation in municipal governments. The study used a descriptive research methodology within a qualitative framework to examine citizen engagement in planning and decision-making processes at the local level. It aims to identify obstacles that hinder their active participation. The findings illustrate that meaningful engagement is limited due to various factors, including a lack of awareness of governance processes, poor access to information, and widespread disinterest caused by a lack of trust in governance institutions. Moreover, physical, economic, and social barriers further restrict the involvement of marginalized people and economically disadvantaged communities. Additionally, public engagement varies according to socio-demographic factors, highlighting persistent disparities in access and representation. The analysis shows that Nepal's policies do a lot to encourage people to become involved, but they haven't been as effective in practice. To close this gap, there is an urgent need to raise awareness, make it easier to obtain reliable information, and confront structural and socioeconomic problems. The study findings recommend that to involve more people in the local governance process, it's important to build trust and illustrate the real benefits of involvement.

Keywords: citizen, governance, participation, accountability, planning